

phaee
Closing Inequality Gaps

2019 - 2023

ANNUAL REPORT

Embark on a journey of impact with us! This report reflects a year of positive change, made possible by your unwavering support. Together, we shape a healthier Nigeria. Thank you for being part of our story.

PHAAE.ORG

Letter from our Founder & program director

As we reflect on the accomplishments of the past year, I am filled with gratitude for the strides we have made toward our shared vision of fostering a healthier Nigeria. It is my pleasure to present the annual report of our organization, highlighting the impactful work that has been achieved with your unwavering support.

Our commitment to ensuring access to safe and clean water, promoting proper sanitation, and encouraging effective hygiene practices has driven us to make a meaningful difference in the lives of those we serve, particularly in underserved communities and among vulnerable populations.

The impact we have made would not have been possible without the unwavering support of our dedicated volunteers, partners, and generous donors. We extend our heartfelt gratitude to each one of you who has been a part of our journey.

As we look ahead, there is much more work to be done. We invite you to continue supporting our mission by making a contribution, no matter how big or small. Your donation will directly contribute to creating a lasting impact on the lives of those in need.

In the face of the challenges that persist, your belief in our cause is a source of motivation for us to strive for even greater accomplishments. Together, we can make a difference and build a healthier, more resilient Nigeria.

Thank you for your continued support.

Sincerely,

Uc-Okonmah
Founder / Program director

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1. Introduction

Public Health Aid Awareness & Education Organization (PHAAE), registered in 2015, is a non-profit organization with its headquarters in Abuja, Nigeria. We are dedicated to addressing the water and sanitation needs of underserved communities, focusing on sustainable solutions and behavior change. Through our various programs and projects, we aim to create a positive impact on public health, hygiene practices, and environmental sustainability. One of our main strategies to achieve our goal of public health is to create channels of information and education with host communities with the aim of increasing their awareness, knowledge, and literacy of health.

Aid and hygiene kits

In cases of clear or desperate need, we offer aid and assistance measures through the construction of water taps and clean water storage or the provision of sanitary items like toilets and trash cans.

We also produce and provide hygiene kits, of which there are four variations: kid's kit for good hand hygiene (K2), the purity kit for menstrual hygiene management, the emergency hygiene kit, and the family kit.

Health education and hygiene promotion

As informed and research-based health educators, we work to increase health awareness among people, contributing to behavior change and the adoption of a positive attitude regarding wellbeing. We generate informative visuals such as cartoon stories for children, game books, and educational coloring books for elementary school pupils.

Media / digital efficiency

Both creativity and effective media planning drive our programs. Using the media as an ally, we are quick to spread campaign messaging reaching vast coverage. Our digital tools include Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram, YouTube and the official PHAAE website which all serve to disseminate our work and spark global discussions.

Current follower count:

> 1500
followers

Types of posts:

- Informative facts
- Questions / quizzes
- Work of PHAAE

► Facebook

Total number of followers: 466

Reach: 124

Business comparison:

- **Content interactions:** lower than other businesses (4 vs typically 56 on other pages).
- **New followers:** lower than other businesses (1 vs typically 6 on other pages).
- **How often PHAAE publishes compared to other businesses in the same category:** PHAAE is between the 50th and the 75th percentile. The total number of followers is similar to other businesses in the same category

Post with the highest reach:

https://m.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid=pfbid0317WzDephitjdMxPX34MPKwXrqdyTyeTnBFTPkznpEt6csqUg3EuW6kzaoGYzNjYjl&id=2054281678230400

- **Reach:** 1013
- **Reactions:** 14
- **Comments:** 2
- **Shares:** 3

► Instagram

Total number of followers: 350

Reach: 65

Business comparison:

Content interactions: interactions are similar to other businesses.

New follower: lower than other businesses (6 vs typically 14 on other pages).

	FOLLOWERS	REACH	REACTIONS	SHARES
	466	1013	14	3
	350	359	4	2
	46	640	3	2
	655	452	2	3

- HIGHEST REACH POST INFORMATION -

- How often PHAAE publishes compared to other businesses in the same category: PHAAE is lower than the 25th percentile. The total number of followers is similar to other businesses in the same category.

Post with the highest reach:

https://www.instagram.com/reel/CqAl3EWsbp_

- **Reach:** 359
- **Likes:** 4
- **Comments:** 4
- **Shares:** 2

► **Twitter**

Total number of followers: 46

Post with the highest reach:

https://twitter.com/phaae_org/status/1652992290674155522?s=20

- **Impressions:** 640
- **Engagement rate:** 5%
- **Reactions:** 30
- **Reposts:** 2

► **LinkedIn**

Total number of followers: 655

Reach: 452

Post with the highest reach:

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/phaae_watercrisis-publichealth-sdg6-activity-7063875590084304896-Hzuh?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_ios

- **Impressions:** 31
- **Unique impressions:** 24
- **Engagement rate:** 16.1%
- **Reactions:** 2
- **Reposts:** 3

Entertainment education

Through entertainment education, we convey health messages to our stakeholders in the form of music, drama, or dance.

User-friendly interventions, programs & community practice

We adopt user-friendly and community focused interventions and program evaluation metrics. We value partnering with communities to understand and address critical barriers to health equity.

Health promotion

Health Promotion involves enabling people to increase control of their health through advocacy and inter-sectoral collaboration. This encompasses dissemination of simple health facts but also more complex information and skills on how to prevent diseases and illnesses, collaborative workshops, and multi-topic seminars.

Advocacy

We create user-friendly, factual advocacy tools targeted mainly at Nigerian policymakers and various stakeholders.

Partnerships

We form productive partnerships with other non-profits and corporate profit-making organizations to achieve a common goal. Our partners include academia, local community, and donors among others.

Social & behavioral change communication

SBCC is the strategic use of communication to promote positive health outcomes based on proven health theories and models of behavior change we are able to achieve defined behavioral objectives through inter-personal channels and mass media.

2. Mission and vision

OUR MISSION

To foster a healthier Nigeria by ensuring access to safe and clean water, promoting proper sanitation, and encouraging effective hygiene practices, with a focus on underserved communities and vulnerable populations.

OUR VISION

To be recognized globally as the leading non-profit organization providing water, sanitation facilities, and education to rural communities in Nigeria and other developing countries in Africa.

OUR CORE VALUES

- ▶ Accountability
- ▶ Transparency
- ▶ Learning
- ▶ Professionalism

3. Programs and project

School WASH project

The School WASH Project focuses on installing clean water facilities, sanitation systems, and toilets in schools. In addition to infrastructure development, we conduct hygiene education and health promotion activities to instill healthy habits among students and staff.

The project started as a hygiene promotion program in which pupils were taught best handwashing practices, menstrual hygiene management, and more, but upon arriving at the first school for implementation, we discovered there was no running water or toilets.

Further investigation revealed that 72 local schools had neither running water nor a toilet facility. Immediately, we began a project overhaul. The inclusion of other intervention activities and project redesign to install clean water facilities and safe sanitation systems before hygiene promotion culminated in the school WASH project.

This program was first implemented in two primary schools, LEA Takushara and LEA Kunyami and was sponsored by the United States government.

PHAAE has identified sixty-nine (69) more primary schools in urgent need of running water and sanitation systems. Only after provision of these basic facilities can we begin the hygiene promotion and education programs.

We envisage the day when every school in our community has high-quality hygiene facilities and the best environment for pupils to learn and grow.

Hygiene kits distribution

We distribute various hygiene kits to communities in need. These include hand kits, kits for kids, menstrual hygiene management kits, emergency hygiene kits, and family kits. By providing essential hygiene items, we aim to improve hygiene practices and overall well-being.

Menstrual hygiene management

Through our menstrual hygiene management programs, we educate girls and women on proper menstrual hygiene practices and distribute sanitary towels or kits. This initiative aims to promote menstrual health, reduce stigma, and ensure access to hygienic products.

Menstruation is a natural process linked to the reproductive cycle of women and girls. It is a sign of good health and growing up. It is not an illness but if it is not properly managed, it may result in health problems which can be compounded by social, cultural and religious practices.

Often menstruation is a taboo subject not discussed. Ignorance and stigma around menstruation is a global problem and simultaneously endangers the health of individual women and girls.

To manage menstruation hygienically, it is essential that women and girls have access to safe water and sanitation. They need somewhere private to change their sanitary clothes or pads, clean water and soap for hand and cloths washing, and facilities for safe disposal of used materials or a place to dry reusable pads.

PHAAE launched its menstrual hygiene management program amongst adolescent girls and women of the Yangoji community, in Kwali area council.

Education included the need for proper hygiene behaviors during menstruation, the kind of materials used for pads and how often pads should be changed, how and where to dispose pads and what kinds of risks exist if menstrual hygiene is not maintained. The program is often duplicated in schools of disadvantaged communities, internally displaced people's camps, where sanitary towels or our purity kits are distributed to girls.

On May 28, PHAAE joined its partners, WASH united, menstrual hygiene day, and HARP initiative to celebrate menstrual hygiene day. PHAAE visited the junior secondary school,

Galadimawa in Abuja, where it delivered a thorough menstrual hygiene management lecture. The program concluded with the distribution of purity kits for menstrual hygiene management to over 125 girls with the aim to provide a whole term supply of sanitary needs.

Hygiene promotion through schools

We implement hygiene promotion programs among elementary school children, delivering key messages and providing informational materials. By targeting schools, we cultivate a culture of hygiene awareness and behavior change from an early age.

PHAAE BELIEVES THAT CHILDREN ARE STRONG AGENTS OF CHANGE

Children have been shown to spread hygiene behaviors among their peers, parents, and relations at home.

Hygiene promotion at rural market

To address hygiene practices in rural areas, we create awareness on proper hygiene practices and sensitize market committees to adopt hygienic behaviors. By engaging with market communities, we promote positive change at a grassroots level. Rural markets in Nigeria can be dirty, unhygienic, and lacking reliable structures for defecation, urination, and bathing. Many rural markets have privately owned community sanitation facilities which are operational on a use-to-pay basis. Unfortunately, some of these facilities do not provide soap for washing hands, thus people wash their hands with water only. Our team works to create awareness of hygiene practices using posters, leaflets, and other IEC materials. Market committees are sensitized on the importance of adopting hygienic behaviors.

Plastic exchange project

Our plastic exchange project focuses on addressing plastic waste dumping that contaminates local water ways and eventually oceans through the promotion of recycling and the creation of brand ambassadors in various social environments. This initiative aims to reduce environmental pollution while creating awareness about responsible water management.

The project also demonstrates the economic benefits of engaging in the recycling of plastic waste. Finally, the project shows a positive correlation between the recycling of plastic products and the reduction of carbon emissions into the air caused by the production of new plastic products.

Our aim is to create and empower plastic exchange brand ambassadors in schools, residential estates, places of worship, restaurants and eateries, and office environments. At planned events, the brand ambassadors will support the spread of awareness of our project in their areas of influence.

Through carefully coordinated enlightenment workshops and campaigns in the above-mentioned social environments, plastic exchange aims to promote a reorientation of how waste is disposed of; especially, plastic waste and its long-term negative effect on our local and global environments.

We also want to use this project to create social and economic empowerment for our brand ambassadors by providing incentives for achieving agreed measurable targets and milestones through the course of this project.

We believe that if social groups reinforce and adhere to a culture of plastic recycling there will be a systematic reduction in the production of new plastic materials by manufacturers who rely on fossil fuels and hydrocarbon raw materials for its production, which promotes low carbon growth and pollution in waterways.

Community / school led total sanitation

We adopt the Community-Led Total Sanitation (CLTS) approach to encourage communities to adopt safe and hygienic sanitation practices. By involving community members and schools in decision-making and behavior change activities, we empower them to take ownership of their sanitation facilities.

A lot of communities and schools in Nigeria, both urban and rural, are burdened with open defecation practices. The health risks of this practice are enormous yet very few villages in Nigeria are certified as open defecation free.

Community-Led Total Sanitation (CLTS) or SLTS is an approach which is based on the principle of triggering collective behavior change. In this approach, rural communities are encouraged to take collective action to adopt safe and hygienic sanitation behavior and guarantee that all households have access to safe sanitation facilities.

CLTS focuses on behavior change in sanitation practices rather than construction of sanitation infrastructure. This change in sanitation behaviors is accomplished through a process of social sensitization stimulated by facilitators from within or outside the community. The CLTS approach concentrates on the whole community rather than on individual behaviors. Knowledge of the collective benefit from eliminating open defecation practices can encourage a more cooperative approach. People decide together how they will generate a clean and hygienic environment that benefits everyone. CLTS involves no individual household hardware subsidy and does not prescribe latrine models.

The CLTS approach focuses on eliminating open defecation as a first significant step and entry point for changing behavior. It starts by enabling people to do their own sanitation profile through appraisal, observation, and analysis of their personal practices of open defecation and its effects.

Total sanitation includes a range of behaviors including elimination of open defecation; widespread use of hygienic toilets; handwashing with soap before preparing food and eating, after using the toilet, and after contact with feces or animals; handling food and water in a hygienic manner; and safely disposing of animal and domestic waste.

4. Impact and achievements

Throughout the year, PHAAE has made significant progress in achieving its goals. Some key highlights include:

<p>3000+ students & staff benefited</p>	<p>01 Installed clean water facilities, sanitation systems, and toilets in targeted schools, benefiting 3000+ students and staff.</p>
<p>DISTRIBUTED hygiene kits to communities</p>	<p>02 Distributed hygiene kits to communities in need, promoting proper hygiene practices and improving overall health.</p>
<p>3000+ girls & women reached</p>	<p>03 Reached 3000+ girls & women with menstrual hygiene management programs, ensuring access to hygienic products and reducing stigma.</p>
<p>MULTIPLE educational sessions for children</p>	<p>04 Conducted multiple hygiene promotion programs in several elementary schools, educating children on healthy hygiene practices.</p>
<p>RAISED awareness in rural areas</p>	<p>05 Raised awareness on hygiene practices in some rural markets, sensitizing market committees to adopt hygienic behaviors.</p>
<p>EMPOWERED different communities & schools</p>	<p>06 Empowered communities & schools through the adoption of safe and hygienic sanitation practices under the CLTS approach.</p>

UN water conference 2023

The UN water conference, also known as the world water forum, is a global event organized by the United Nations and other stakeholders to address water-related issues and promote sustainable water management in line with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 6 (SDG 6), which focuses on ensuring availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all. PHAAE had the privilege of contributing to the event's dialogue, bringing a unique African perspective to the event held at the UN Headquarters in New York on the 22nd and 24th of March, 2023.

Syed Jazib Ali, the organization's outreach and advocacy director, shared the following:

“

The idea that the African continent is running out of water has been disproven by recent studies, as below ground, there are enormous water reserves, many of which are refilled yearly and through other surface water sources. There is, however, an issue with persistently underfunded services, making these resources inaccessible. Using groundwater as a source would guarantee that millions of people have access to safe and clean water despite the threat of desertification and other climate issues in the region. The majority of African nations have enough groundwater to support populations for decades to come.

By giving women and children the tools they need for better lives, improving WASH conditions, and increasing funding to local NGOs, the United Nations can help improve clean water access to marginalized communities in West Africa. The governmental institutions in West Africa are not well-equipped and struggle to reach the marginalized communities. This cements the position of community-based NGOs as the most effective grassroots actors.

PHAAE works hand in hand with rural and marginalized communities' grassroots transformational programs. In rural and underserved areas in West Africa, we want to spearhead a grassroots revolution that enables self-sustaining health practices with access to water, sanitation, and hygiene for women and children. We truly believe that improving the availability of clean water and sanitation facilities in isolated and rural communities will help achieve SDG 6's objectives.

”

Cholera prevention strategies webinar

In line with the PHAAE's mandate to promote the UN's SDG 6, promoting access to clean water and sanitation, we hosted a live webinar on cholera prevention strategies on the 30th of October 2021. This event was held in collaboration with the University of South Carolina (USC) Centre for Emerging Pathogens (CEP), a leading voice in infection prevention strategies and best practice response to emerging pathogens.

Dr. Neha Nanda (MD), the founding director of CEP and associate professor of clinical medicine, was the chief speaker and provided a detailed overview of the public health status of cholera, with a focus on Nigeria. The seminar was open to industry actors and the public.

The state of cholera in Nigeria as of 2021 was analyzed: the prevalence of cholera cases was roughly 93,000 and the disease was identified in 31 of the country's 36 states. Although Northern Nigeria was especially hard-hit, there was an overall saturation of the country as 86% of its states reported cholera cases with a 3.5% fatality rate.

The multifunctional prevention approach used by the Global Task Force on Cholera Control (GTFCC) and UNICEF was explored next. The human right to water and sanitation is the foundation of the fight against cholera, and the human rights mainstreaming approach must remain centralized. The UNICEF's WASH (Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene) strategic framework 2016-2030 provides a guideline for realizing universal and equitable water for all. This, in tandem with an end to open defecation and a gender-sensitive approach to the unique needs of women and girls, would strengthen the fight against the disease. This progress relies on sustainable access to services at scale, evidence-based programming, and community monitoring.

Dr. Nanda explored some lessons from previous outbreaks including the 2011 outbreak in Haiti which highlighted the importance of early detection, early response and early treatment as a concerted effort. In this case, although there was a rush to treat patients, prevention was sidelined, and there was a missed chance to stop the spread of the disease.

The following year in South Sudan, the importance of preemptive vaccination and immunization awareness was realized by the evidence dent in the spread of the disease when over 160,000 vaccinations were administered, specifically in the refugee population.

Promoting certain habits worked best at the community level: good personal hygiene, education and awareness, and proper cooking practices.

Dr. Nanda highlighted the importance of grassroots organizations like PHAAE, as essential for prevention at the community level.

ORGANIZATIONS LIKE PHAAE ARE ESSENTIAL FOR PREVENTION AT THE COMMUNITY LEVEL.

Webinar on open defecation

This seminar was held on the 17th of December 2021 in collaboration with the Centre for Emerging Pathogens (CEP) at USC to discuss the practice of open defecation and its implications on public health. It was a high-priority seminar, as public defecation remains a pressing issue in Nigeria's public health landscape. According to the 2021 WASH national outcome routine mapping on the country's sanitation situation, 48 million people in Nigeria practice open defecation and 95 million lack access to even the most basic sanitation facilities. The seminar speakers were Dr. Nanda, the founding director of CEP and associate professor of clinical medicine, Dr Tukur Isma'il, the executive secretary of Zamfara state primary healthcare board, and PHAAE's founder, Uc-Onkonmah.

Dr. Neha acknowledged that the global community has lagged in reaching its goal to eradicate open defecation by 2030 in line with Sustainable Development Goal 6 (SDG 6) on clean water and sanitation. She went on to analyze the scope of this issue, which she called a 'humbling public health emergency'. United Nations agencies like UNICEF and the World Health Organization report that over 673 million people still practiced open defecation, as of 2019.

Ninety percent of this occurs in rural areas, and the number of deaths occurring annually due to diarrheal diseases sits at close to a million, with 800,000 per annum. Lack of access to sanitation remains the main culprit in these cases, and sadly, one thousand children are lost each day to these harsh realities.

In spotlighting Nigeria, Dr. Tukur noted the prevalence of open defecation in the country, with 46 million people engaging in the practice at about 23 percent of the country's population. However, the practice is more concentrated in certain regions resulting in geographical variance.

Dr. Tukur reiterated that the practice is a public health emergency because of its potential to cause diseases and illness. The Nigerian government has tried to make changes at all levels, the national, state, and local government promoted changes at individual and community levels, but there have been numerous challenges. The lack of appropriate technologies and facility options alongside the country's varying geophysical conditions, like the swampy swell and water-locked areas in the south, make constructing proper hygiene facilities challenging for communities with limited resources.

The government agencies making progress on eradicating open defecation are the Ministry of water resources, the Ministry of environmental affairs, the Ministry of health, and the Ministry of agriculture, often in collaboration with international agencies. These interventions are based on providing adequate facilities, education and awareness and proper monitoring of objectives.

Diarrheal diseases linked to open defecation are a significant health issue in Nigeria, particularly among children under five. These diseases are usually caused by ingesting contaminated food or water and exacerbated by living conditions such as overcrowding and the prevalence of urban slums lacking proper sanitation infrastructure, leading to the rapid spread of diarrheal pathogens among residents.

673 million
practiced open defecation

90 %
occurs in rural areas

800 thousand
deaths due to diarrheal diseases

Mrs. Okonmah shared her experience dealing with these issues in the country's capital city, Abuja, also known as the federal capital territory, or FCT, stating that an official declaration of a state of emergency on water sanitation and hygiene in the country was in place, with several area councils in the capital having little or no water access. The FCT Rural Water Supply & Sanitation Agency had declared only three out of ten communities from Bwari towns free from open defecation. Mrs. Okonmah maintained that despite this low number, the greater challenge is maintaining the status within these communities. Things are still bleak in the FCT, as statistics show that 39.4 percent of people living in the FCT practice open defecation. Speaking from her field experience, Mrs. Okonmah discussed hygiene promotional activities for pupils in public schools that often had no water and toilets. The discovery of inadequate water and toilets in schools led to a project overhaul, and the Local Education Authority board was contacted for a list of schools in the AMMAC area council to ascertain the hygiene facilities available. They spoke to the community heads and rulers to understand the reason for construction of schools without toilet facilities. These conversations revealed deeply held behavioral practices and the recognition that many members of the communities did not have hygiene facilities at their place of residence. The seminar ended by exploring the best strategies to end the practice of open defecation, including the promotion of community participation and engagement in sensitization and hygiene promotion to encourage behavior change.

WASH Debate

On 15 March 2023, a WASH (water, sanitation and hygiene) debate was held via webinar by the expert panelists below. The panelists discussed the current challenges and opportunities to improve water and sanitary health access for communities in Africa and globally.

Expected Impact

PHAAE aims to lead a grassroots transformation that enables self-sustaining health practices, inclusive of women and children in rural communities of Africa.

Millions in Africa lack access to enough clean water to drink, yet recent research debunks the myth that the continent is running out of water. There are vast water reserves under people’s feet, many of which are replenished yearly by rainfall and other surface water. Still, they cannot be accessed because of the chronically underfunded services. Tapping into groundwater would ensure millions have access to safe and clean water, even with the uncertainty of the climate crisis.

PHAAE, in the past, has delivered successful drilling projects providing clean groundwater access to marginalized communities. With international funding, we were able to install hand pumps that were more sustainable than tube wells, which use unaffordable fuel pumping generators. The solar panels to support the pumping generators are sustainable but require expensive and high maintenance, which makes it non-inclusive for the rural population.

According to our expert analysis, our groundwater access for WASH projects in the village schools directly impact 200-400 people and indirectly 1000-2000 families in every community, as women and children no longer need to travel long distances to the streams to fetch dirty and unsafe water. The whole community fetches water from the hand pumps installed in the schools as schools are not fenced and are usually centrally located.

5. Financial summary

In the fiscal year 2022-2023, Public Health Aid Awareness & Education Organization raised over 4 million Naira in donations, demonstrating the support and trust of our donors and stakeholders. We utilized these funds effectively to implement our programs, support projects, and cover operational expenses.

6. Partnerships and collaborations

Public Health Aid Awareness & Education Organization partners and donors include US Government, United Nations Volunteers, WASH United, Global Handwashing Partnership, and Keck School of Medicine of USC.

PHAAE values collaborative efforts and actively seeks partnerships with other non-profit organizations and corporate entities. By joining forces, we can achieve common goals, leverage resources, and maximize our impact. We extend our gratitude to all our partners for their contributions and support.

Keck School of
Medicine of USC

7. Fundraising and support

We are grateful for the generous support we have received from individuals, organizations, and the community. Our dedicated team of over 165 volunteers has been instrumental in driving our mission forward.

8. Events and convening

PHAAE organizes thought leadership events on issues affecting adolescent girls, women, children, and communities. Through these events, we raise awareness, facilitate dialogue, and promote collaborative solutions. We have also worked on grassroots projects in marginalized and rural communities, focusing on schools without access to clean water.

9. Staff and recruitment

PHAAE, a non-governmental, non-profit organization registered in Nigeria in 2015, strives to hire people who are extraordinary at what they do and ready to help the organization deliver on its work affecting women, adolescent girls, and children in Africa.

Working at PHAAE will help you learn how to use your skill set to improve outreach, create content, run programs, and more, all while impacting the lives of people in need.

From 2019 to 2022, the organization has worked with a pool of qualified personnel and volunteers to deliver its programs on Water and Sanitation, Hygiene and Education, focusing on adolescent girls, women and communities.

Some of the staff at PHAAE include:

■ **Uc-Okonmah**

Founder / Program director

■ **Sophie Larrouy**

Program officer

■ **Chinasa J. Orji ESQ**

Director, legal

■ **Syed Jazib Ali**

Outreach & advocacy director

■ **Irene Nnacho**

Program officer

■ **Asma Bouach**

UX/UI designer

We say goodbye to Dick de Jong, technical advisor, who recently passed away.

10. Volunteers

“ Thank you to our generous volunteers who have allowed PHAAE to make such a profound impact on enabling inclusive WASH access to rural communities in Africa ”

PHAAE has benefitted from the support of more than 165 volunteers working on a variety of projects and contributing to a community of citizens who support our cause. There are currently 70 active volunteers, across the world, from a diversity of backgrounds.

A group of four online volunteers with expertise in social media, content creation for popular social media platforms, advertising, graphic design and blogging have supported the administration of PHAAE's Social Media Platforms.

Another team of six online volunteers with experience in report writing have also supported the organization with help to write annual reports respectively for 2019 to 2020, 2021 to 2022.

How To Volunteer

Please check our [website](#) or the [UN Volunteers platform](#) for volunteer opportunities.

11. Conclusion

The past year has been remarkable for the Public Health Aid Awareness & Education Organization, as we have continued to make a positive difference in the lives of individuals and communities. We remain committed to our mission of providing water, sanitation facilities, and education to underserved areas. With the support of our stakeholders, partners, and volunteers, we will continue to expand our reach, enhance our programs, and improve public health and hygiene standards.

For more detailed information and updates on our programs, initiatives, and impact, please visit our website at www.phaae.org

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Closing Inequality Gaps

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